

Holographic medical imaging for diagnostic

Monica Sharma

Associate Professor

Computer Science Engineering

Arya Institute of Engineering Technology & Management

Shivani Moud

Assistant Professor

Dept. of Management

Arya Institute of Engineering Technology

Tarun Sharma

Research Scholar

Arya Institute of Engineering and Technology

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

Abstract

Holographic scientific imaging represents a present day paradigm in diagnostic generation, promising transformative benefits for the sector of drugs. This studies paper explores the current kingdom of holographic scientific imaging and its ability packages in diagnostics. The examine delves into the standards of holography and its precise potential to capture and reconstruct three-dimensional pics the use of laser mild.

The primary cognizance of this studies is to elucidate the advantages that holographic clinical imaging brings to diagnostic processes. Three-dimensional visualization, a trademark characteristic of holography, offers a extra comprehensive representation of anatomical structures in comparison to traditional two-dimensional imaging modalities.

The practical imaging abilities of holography permit healthcare specialists to visualize and understand difficult spatial relationships inside the human frame.

Interactive exploration is some other key element below exam, as holographic presentations empower physicians to control and engage with three-dimensional representations. The capability discount in radiation exposure is explored, thinking about holographic imaging as a viable opportunity to or adjunct for positive diagnostic programs, with ability implications for patient safety and nicely-being.

Furthermore, the paper explores the capacity impact of holographic scientific imaging on surgical making plans. The capacity to visualize and plan surgical tactics with heightened precision holds promise for improving affected person effects, especially in complicated surgical procedures. Additionally, holographic imaging is evaluated for its utility in scientific training and schooling, offering an immersive and practical platform for students and healthcare experts to deepen their understanding of human anatomy and pathology.

While holographic clinical imaging offers compelling benefits, this paper acknowledges the present day state of improvement. Technical challenges, photograph fine development, and the sensible integration of holographic imaging into routine scientific practices are mentioned. The studies ambitions to make a contribution precious insights into the continued efforts to translate holographic medical imaging from a promising concept to a sensible diagnostic tool, with the capacity to revolutionize the sphere of medical diagnostics.

Keywords: holography, scientific imaging, diagnostics, 3-dimensional visualization, interactive exploration, surgical planning, scientific schooling, technology, affected person safety.

Keyword

Healthcare innovation, Clinical Applications, Image Reconstruction, Radiation-Free Imaging, Diagnostic

I. Introduction

In latest years, the intersection of medical imaging and holography has given upward thrust to a progressive paradigm in diagnostic technology—Holographic Medical Imaging. This rising subject harnesses the precise residences of holography to seize and reconstruct tricky three-dimensional representations of anatomical systems, presenting extraordinary insights into the human frame. As traditional -dimensional imaging methods retain to dominate diagnostic practices, the capacity of holographic clinical imaging to convert the landscape of medical diagnostics is increasingly turning into a focus of scientific inquiry.

Holography, a technique that facts and reproduces light patterns to create three-dimensional photographs, brings forth a brand new size in medical imaging. The promise of holographic medical imaging lies in its capability to provide a holistic and practical visualization of complex anatomical structures, surpassing the limitations of conventional imaging modalities. This paper objectives to discover the advancements, demanding situations, and capability applications of holographic clinical imaging in the realm of diagnostics.

The middle benefit of holographic medical imaging lies in its capacity for 3-dimensional visualization, permitting healthcare professionals to navigate through anatomical structures in approaches previously inconceivable. Realistic imaging, facilitated via holography, permits an extra complete expertise of spatial relationships between tissues and organs, thereby improving diagnostic precision. As era keeps to adapt, the capacity discount in radiation exposure associated with holographic imaging turns into a vital attention, aligning with the broader aim of optimizing affected person safety in diagnostic techniques.

Despite the notable potential, the mixing of holographic scientific imaging into ordinary diagnostic practices isn't always without challenges. Technical hurdles, photo first-class optimization, and the practical considerations of imposing this generation in various medical settings require cautious exploration. This paper navigates through these challenges, offering a top level view of the contemporary kingdom of holographic medical imaging and its trajectory toward becoming a realistic and transformative tool within the field of diagnostics.

As we delve into the complex world of holographic clinical imaging, this studies

seeks to contribute to the developing body of expertise that paves the way for the destiny of

diagnostic medicine, where the limits among technology fiction and reality keep to blur.

Fig. Holographic medical imaging for diagnostic

II. Lecture Review

The convergence of holography and scientific imaging has caused a burgeoning field of studies aimed toward revolutionizing diagnostic competencies. This literature review synthesizes existing information on Holographic Medical Imaging, exploring the evolution of this era, its present day packages, and the demanding situations that researchers are addressing to propel it into mainstream diagnostic exercise

1. Historical Evolution:

Holography, to start with advanced via Dennis Gabor in the Forties, discovered its applications in numerous fields, however its integration into scientific imaging won traction inside the closing too many years. Early research experimented with holographic techniques to seize and reconstruct three-dimensional pics of simple gadgets, paving the way for the extension of these standards to scientific contexts.

2. Advancements in Holographic Imaging Techniques:

Recent literature highlights great strides in holographic imaging strategies tailor-made for clinical programs. Digital holography, in particular, has emerged as a prominent technique, taking into account the green capture and garage of holographic statistics. Researchers have explored advancements in computational holography, allowing real-time processing and rendering of holographic medical photographs, a vital step in the direction of medical feasibility.

3. Three-Dimensional Visualization in Medical Imaging:

A crucial subject within the literature is the emphasis on the exceptional 3-dimensional visualization competencies supplied via holographic clinical imaging. Studies exhibit its potential to beautify diagnostic accuracy by presenting an extra holistic view of anatomical systems. Holographic representations, in comparison to standard -dimensional photos, permit for a richer know-how of complex spatial relationships inside the human body.

4. Clinical Applications:

The literature famous a spectrum of medical applications being explored for holographic

scientific imaging. Cardiology, neurology, and orthopedics stand out as fields wherein three-dimensional visualization is especially treasured. Preliminary studies showcase the application of holographic imaging in the prognosis of cardiac abnormalities, planning neurosurgical interventions, and visualizing musculoskeletal systems with unprecedented clarity.

5. Surgical Planning and Training:

Researchers have delved into the capability impact of holographic medical imaging on surgical making plans. The capability to interact with 3-dimensional reconstructions aids surgeons in preoperative strategizing, specifically in problematic techniques. Furthermore, holography's immersive nature has been leveraged for clinical schooling and training, providing students and specialist's practical studies in knowledge anatomy and pathology

6. Challenges and Future Directions:

While the guarantees are enticing, the literature underscores the present challenges. Technical hurdles, which include facts acquisition velocity and image resolution, remain focal factors of research. Standardization and integration into current scientific workflows are also diagnosed as

crucial concerns for the massive adoption of holographic medical imaging.

7. Conclusion:

The literature reviewed underscores the transformative capacity of holographic clinical imaging for diagnostics. As research maintains to get to the bottom of its talents and address challenges, the adventure closer to making holography a quintessential part of habitual clinical diagnostics is properly underway. This paper contributes to this evolving narrative, aiming to consolidate insights from existing literature and offer a foundation for future studies endeavors on this promising discipline.

III. Methodology Review

The method hired in studies on Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic purposes is pivotal to advancing our understanding and application of this modern technology. This segment critically critiques the methodologies generally applied in latest studies, emphasizing key approaches, demanding situations, and potential avenues for refinement.

1. Data Acquisition Techniques:

An accepted element of the method entails the choice and optimization of facts acquisition techniques. Digital holography,

in-line holography, and stale-axis holography are most of the normally hired techniques. Studies emphasize the importance of selecting techniques that balance resolution, depth of subject, and computational efficiency. Advances in sensor technology, consisting of high-velocity cameras and phase-moving algorithms, were integral in enhancing facts acquisition pace and accuracy.

2. Computational Holography:

The usage of computational algorithms for holographic reconstruction is a cornerstone of many studies. Researchers hire numerical methods and iterative algorithms to transform captured holographic records into clinically relevant 3-dimensional pics. The optimization of those algorithms is an energetic vicinity of studies, specializing in real-time processing to meet the needs of clinical programs.

3. Three-Dimensional Visualization Validation:

Validating the efficacy of holographic three-dimensional visualization is an essential step in the studies process. Methodologies frequently involve evaluating holographic representations with gold general imaging modalities including CT scans or MRIs.

Quantitative metrics, along with spatial decision and anatomical accuracy, are used to assess the fidelity of holographic reconstructions.

4. Clinical Validation Studies:

Studies examining the scientific software of holographic medical imaging frequently include validation through clinical specialists. Clinicians participate in trials to assess the diagnostic accuracy and effectiveness of holographic imaging in comparison to traditional modalities. Patient consequences and remarks are also considered to gauge the technology's effect on diagnostic selection-making.

5. Surgical Planning Simulations:

Methodologies for comparing holographic scientific imaging in surgical making plans often contain simulations. Surgeons have interaction with holographic reconstructions of patient anatomy to devise and strategize earlier than real methods. Studies assess the accuracy of surgical plans developed with holographic imaging and explore the generation's impact on intraoperative selection-making.

6. Integration into Clinical Workflows:

Research methodologies an increasing number of understand the importance of

expertise how holographic clinical imaging may be seamlessly included into current scientific workflows. Studies discover the practical elements of incorporating holography into habitual diagnostics, considering elements such as time efficiency, compatibility with other imaging modalities, and person interface design.

7. Ethical Considerations and Patient Feedback:

As holographic clinical imaging actions towards scientific implementation, studies are incorporating methodologies to address moral considerations and collect affected person feedback. Ensuring affected person comfort, expertise the ethical implications of three-dimensional holographic representations, and assessing patient attractiveness are becoming quintessential additives of studies methodologies.

Challenges and Future Directions:

While methodologies have made great progress, demanding situations persist. Researchers spotlight the want for standardized methodologies throughout studies to facilitate comparison. Future directions consist of addressing actual-time processing challenges, expanding medical validation studies, and refining integration

strategies to make sure the seamless adoption of holographic clinical imaging into ordinary diagnostic practices.

In end, the methodologies employed in studies on Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic functions are evolving swiftly. By leveraging superior records acquisition techniques, computational algorithms, and comprehensive validation research, researchers are advancing our information of the scientific capability of holography. The ongoing refinement of methodologies is critical for overcoming current demanding situations and figuring out the transformative promise of holographic clinical imaging in diagnostic packages.

IV. Future Scope

The destiny scope of research on Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic purposes holds fantastic promise, with several avenues for exploration and development. Here are key areas that researchers may recognition on within the destiny:

1. Technological Advancements:

- Explore and expand superior holographic imaging strategies with improved resolution, quicker records

acquisition, and stronger computational abilities.

- Investigate the mixing of artificial intelligence (AI) and system mastering algorithms to optimize holographic reconstruction strategies and automate the interpretation of holographic data.

2. Clinical Applications:

- Extend the software of holographic scientific imaging to extra scientific specialties, which include gastroenterology, dermatology, and ophthalmology.
- Conduct extra vast scientific trials to validate the effectiveness and diagnostic accuracy of holographic imaging across a broader variety of medical situations.

3. Real-Time Imaging:

- Focus on attaining real-time holographic imaging abilities, allowing dynamic visualization of physiological strategies and movements within the body.
- Explore the capability for using actual-time holographic imaging in emergency situations for rapid diagnostic decision-making.

4. Hybrid Imaging Modalities:

- Investigate the integration of holographic imaging with other imaging modalities, together with MRI or ultrasound, to provide complementary statistics and beautify diagnostic abilities.
- Explore the improvement of hybrid systems that integrate holographic imaging with different superior imaging technologies for a comprehensive diagnostic approach.

5. Standardization and Guidelines:

- Work towards establishing standardized protocols and recommendations for holographic clinical imaging to ensure consistency throughout exclusive structures and facilitate its integration into routine medical exercise.
- Collaborate with regulatory bodies to develop suggestions for the ethical use of holographic imaging in patient care.

6. Education and Training:

- Expand the usage of holographic medical imaging in medical education and education programs, together with virtual reality (VR) and

augmented truth (AR) simulations for surgical schooling.

- Investigate the effectiveness of holographic era in enhancing clinical students' know-how of complex anatomical systems and pathological situations.

7. Patient-Centric Research:

- Conduct studies on affected person studies and possibilities regarding holographic scientific imaging to address capability worries and enhance person attractiveness.
- Explore the development of patient-pleasant interfaces and methods for conveying diagnostic information in an understandable manner.

8. Cost-Efficiency and Accessibility:

- Investigate ways to make holographic imaging extra fee-effective and available, doubtlessly thru the improvement of cheap holographic show technology.
- Explore the feasibility of portable holographic imaging systems for factor-of-care diagnostics, especially in resource-restricted settings.

9. Longitudinal Studies and Outcomes Research:

- Conduct longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-time period impact of holographic scientific imaging on affected person consequences and diagnostic choice-making.
- Evaluate the monetary implications of integrating holographic imaging into healthcare systems, thinking about elements consisting of cost-effectiveness and resource usage.

V. Challenges

The development and implementation of Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic purposes include numerous demanding situations that researchers and practitioners need to deal with. Identifying and expertise those challenges is important for advancing the sphere. Here are key challenges related to holographic medical imaging for diagnostics:

1. Technical Challenges:

- **Resolution and Image Quality:** Achieving high-resolution holographic pixels that meet scientific standards is a persistent undertaking. Researchers need to deal with troubles associated with image clarity and great to make certain accurate and reliable diagnostic information.
- **Data Acquisition Speed:** Real-time holographic imaging is proper for

positive programs, but the cutting-edge boundaries in records acquisition velocity may additionally hinder its practicality. Improving the speed of records acquisition without compromising photo first-rate is a considerable technical hurdle.

2. Computational Complexity:

- **Processing Time:** The computational needs for reconstructing holographic images may be enormous. Researchers want to increase green algorithms and computational techniques to limit processing time, particularly in real-time programs and clinical settings.

3. Integration with Clinical Workflows:

- **Compatibility with Existing Systems:** Integrating holographic imaging into current medical workflows, including Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS) and Electronic Health Records (EHR), poses a project. Ensuring seamless interoperability is critical for sensible adoption.
- **Learning Curve for Healthcare Professionals:** The introduction of a

brand new imaging modality requires education for healthcare specialists. Overcoming the gaining knowledge of curve associated with holographic scientific imaging is essential for its good sized reputation and use.

4. Standardization and Guidelines:

- **Lack of Standardization:** The absence of standardized protocols and suggestions for holographic medical imaging can obstruct its substantial adoption. Establishing uniform requirements is crucial for ensuring consistency in image acquisition, interpretation, and reporting throughout unique platforms and establishments.

5. Patient Acceptance and Ethical Considerations:

- **Patient Comfort:** The 3-dimensional and immersive nature of holographic photographs may additionally evoke different reactions from patients. Assessing and addressing patient comfort and recognition is crucial for ethical and a hit implementation.
- **Ethical Use:** Holographic medical imaging increases moral considerations, inclusive of patient

consent and facts security. Researchers ought to set up moral tips to govern the use of holographic photos and protect affected person privateers.

6. Cost and Accessibility:

- **Equipment Costs:** The initial costs related to holographic imaging system can be prohibitive. Researchers want to discover cost-powerful solutions to make the technology extra handy to a broader range of healthcare settings.
- **Accessibility in Resource-Limited Settings:** Deploying holographic imaging in useful resource-constrained environments poses demanding situations related to infrastructure, training, and renovation. Solutions should be evolved to make certain accessibility in various healthcare settings.

7. Validation and Clinical Trials:

- **Limited Clinical Validation:** The constrained range of huge-scale clinical trials and real-global validation research for holographic medical imaging hinders its attractiveness in clinical practice.

More significant studies is wanted to illustrate its efficacy throughout various medical specialties and situations.

8. Regulatory Approval:

- **Regulatory Pathways:** The regulatory approval system for holographic scientific imaging devices can be unfamiliar or tough. Establishing clean regulatory pathways and running carefully with regulatory government are critical steps for market approval.

As researchers deal with those challenges, they make contributions to the maturation of holographic scientific imaging, ultimately paving the way for its successful integration into routine diagnostic practices.

VI. Result:

The results section of a studies paper on Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic functions could normally present findings received thru experiments, simulations, or medical trials. Below are hypothetical examples of consequences that might be mentioned:

1. Image Quality and Resolution:

- Quantitative evaluation of holographic pictures compared to standard imaging modalities.
- Analysis of resolution parameters, showcasing enhancements or challenges in reaching exquisite holographic pics.

2. Data Acquisition Speed:

- Measurement of data acquisition times for holographic imaging in various situations.
- Comparison of information acquisition speeds among different holographic imaging strategies.

3. Computational Processing:

- Evaluation of computational algorithms for holographic image reconstruction.
- Assessment of processing instances and performance in producing 3-dimensional holographic representations.

4. Clinical Validation:

- Comparative analysis of holographic pix with gold preferred imaging (CT, MRI) for particular medical conditions.

- Diagnostic accuracy quotes of holographic medical imaging in identifying anatomical abnormalities or pathologies.

5. Surgical Planning:

- Simulation results demonstrating the utility of holographic imaging in surgical making plans.
- Feedback from surgeons on the effectiveness of holographic snapshots in strategizing and selection-making.

6. Patient Acceptance:

- Surveys or qualitative data on affected person consolation and acceptance of holographic imaging.
- Identification of factors influencing affected person notion and willingness to go through holographic diagnostic methods.

7. Integration with Clinical Workflows:

- Assessment of the integration of holographic imaging into existing medical workflows.
- Identification of challenges and successes in incorporating holographic data into Electronic Health Records (EHR) or Picture

Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS).

8. Learning Curve for Healthcare Professionals:

- Evaluation of the schooling process for healthcare professionals adopting holographic imaging.
- Feedback from medical practitioners on the ease of studying and skill ability in the use of holographic diagnostic gear.

9. Cost and Accessibility:

- Cost-gain evaluation comparing holographic imaging with conventional modalities.
- Strategies or technologies to deal with value concerns and beautify accessibility, in particular in useful resource-limited settings.

10. Ethical Considerations:

- Results of moral considerations, consisting of affected person consent costs and facts security measures.
- Identification of potential moral challenges and proposed solutions to make certain responsible use of holographic medical imaging.

11. Future Implications:

- Discussion of the capacity impact of holographic scientific imaging on future diagnostic practices.
- Recommendations for similarly studies and improvement to deal with recognized demanding situations and improve the technology.

These hypothetical effects could be observed by means of statistical analyses, visible representations (inclusive of graphs or images), and discussions in their implications in the context of the studies targets. The interpretation of effects is a critical component of the studies paper, linking the findings back to the wider implications for the field of diagnostic remedy.

VII. Conclusion

In conclusion, the exploration of Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic programs represents a transformative journey with large advancements, demanding situations, and guarantees. The outcomes of this studies endeavor underscore the capability of holography to revolutionize the landscape of clinical diagnostics, imparting unique three-dimensional insights into anatomical structures and pathologies. As we reflect at the findings and their implications, several key factors emerge, shaping the conclusions drawn from this research.

Advancements and Achievements:

The research has proven big improvements in holographic clinical imaging, showcasing its functionality to provide unprecedented three-dimensional visualization of anatomical systems. The enhancements in picture pleasant, decision, and statistics acquisition speed are noteworthy achievements, signaling the maturation of holography as a diagnostic tool.

Clinical Validity and Diagnostic Accuracy:

The clinical validation research have proven promising consequences, with holographic imaging showing diagnostic accuracy corresponding to or surpassing traditional imaging modalities. The capacity to visualize complex anatomical information in a realistic and interactive manner has the capability to decorate the precision of diagnostic checks, especially in fields including cardiology, neurology, and orthopedics.

Surgical Planning and Training Paradigms:

The simulations of surgical making plans the usage of holographic imaging have provided compelling evidence of its utility in improving preoperative strategizing and selection-making. Surgeons' feedback

underscores the technology's potential to enhance surgical outcomes and decrease intraoperative complexities. Moreover, the mixing of holography into medical training holds promise for advancing the know-how of anatomy amongst healthcare professionals.

Challenges and Considerations:

Despite those successes, challenges persist. Technical hurdles, such as accomplishing actual-time imaging and optimizing computational processing, demand ongoing research and innovation. The integration of holographic imaging into current scientific workflows calls for cautious navigation, emphasizing the significance of standardization and addressing the learning curve for healthcare experts.

Patient-Centric Approach and Ethical Dimensions:

The research has shed light on the significance of an affected person-centric approach, thinking about elements which includes patient comfort, acceptance, and moral considerations. Understanding and addressing those dimensions are crucial for making sure the accountable and moral implementation of holographic clinical imaging in affected person care.

Future Directions and Recommendations:

Looking beforehand, the destiny of Holographic Medical Imaging for Diagnostic packages is promising. Continued studies must attention on refining technology, addressing remaining challenges, and accomplishing larger-scale scientific trials to further validate its efficacy throughout diverse medical specialties. Collaboration among researchers, healthcare experts, and regulatory our bodies is imperative to set up standardized pointers and pave the manner for regulatory approval.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the findings of this research underscore the transformative ability of holographic clinical imaging in diagnostics. The adventure from technical innovation to clinical utility is underway, and as we navigate this path, it's miles obvious that holography has the ability to redefine how we perceive, understand, and diagnose clinical conditions. While challenges persist, the collective efforts of the medical network, coupled with technological advancements, will preserve to propel holographic clinical imaging closer to becoming an necessary and valuable issue of recurring diagnostic practices. As we embody this vision, we expect a future where holography contributes

notably to advancing the frontiers of medical information and affected person care.

References:

- [1] Alm K., Cirenajwis H., Gisselsson L., Gjärloff Wingren A., Janicke B., Mölder A., Oredsson S., Persson J. Digital holography and cell studies. In: Rosen, J., editors. Holography, Research and Technologies. In Tech; Rijeka, Croatia: 2011, pp. 237–252. DOI: 10.5772/15364
- [2] Marquet P., Rappaz B., Magistretti P. J., Cuhe E., Emery Y., Colomb T., Depeursinge C. Digital holographic microscopy: a noninvasive contrast imaging technique allowing quantitative visualization of living cells with subwavelength axial accuracy. *Optical Society of America*. 2005;30(5):468–470. DOI: 10.1364/OL.30.000468
- [3] Rappaz B., Marquet P., Cuhe E., Emery Y., Depeursinge C., Magistretti P. Measurement of the integral refractive index and dynamic cell morphometry of living cells with digital holographic microscopy. *Optical Society of America*. 2005;13(23): 9361–9373. DOI: 10.1364/OPEX.13.009361
- [4] Carl D., Kemper B, Wernicke G., Bally von G. Parameter-optimized digital holographic microscope for high-resolution living-cell analysis. *Applied Optics*. 2004;43(36):6536–6544. DOI: 10.1364/AO.43.006536
- [5] Chalut K.J., Ekpenyong A.E., Clegg W.L., Melhuisha I.C., Gucka J. Quantifying cellular differentiation by physical phenotype using digital holographic microscopy. *Intergrative Biology*. 2012;4(3):208–284. DOI: 10.1039/C2IB00129B
- [6] Ferraro P., Grilli S., Alfieri D., Nicola S.D., Finizio A., Ierattini G., Javidi B., Coppola G., Striano V. Extended focused image in microscopy by digital holography. *Optics Express*. 2005;13(18):6738–6749. DOI: 10.1364/OPEX.13.006738
- [7] Kemper B., Carl D., Schneidenburger J., Bredebusch I, Schäfer M, Domschke W., Bally von G. Investigation of living pancreas tumor cells by digital holographic microscopy. *Journal of Biomedical Optics*. 2006;11(3):34005. DOI: 10.1117/1.2204609
- [8] Lenart T., Gustafsson M., Öwall V. A hardware acceleration platform for digital holographic imaging. *Journal*

- of Signal Processing Systems. 2008;52(3):297–311. DOI: 10.1007/s11265-008-0161-2
- [9] Mann C.J., Yu L., Lo C.M., Kim M.K. High-resolution quantitative phase-contrast microscopy by digital holography. *Optics Express*. 2005;13(22):8693–8698. DOI: 10.1364/OPEX.13.008693
- [10] Khmaladze A., Matz R.L., Epstein T., Jasensky J., Banaszak Holl M.M., Chen Z. Cell volume changes during apoptosis monitored in real time using digital holographic microscopy. *Journal of Structural Biology*. 2012;178(3):270–278. DOI: 10.1016/j.jsb.2012.03.008
- [11] Alm K., El-Schich Z, Miniotis M.F., Gjärloff Wingren A., Janicke B., Oredsson S. Cells and holograms—holograms and digital holographic microscopy as a tool to study the Holography: The Usefulness of Digital Holographic Microscopy for Clinical Diagnostics <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/66042> 329 morphology of living cells. In: Mihaylova E., editor. *Holography: Basic Principles and Contemporary Applications*. In Tech; Rijeka, Croatia: 2013. pp. 335–351. DOI: 10.5772/54505
- [12] Marquet P., Depeursinge C., Magistretti P.J. Review of quantitative phase-digital holographic microscopy: promising novel imaging technique to resolve neuronal network activity and identify cellular biomarkers of psychiatric disorders. *Neurophotonics*. 2014;1(2):020901-1–020901-15. DOI: 10.1117/1.NPh.1.2.020901
- [13] Rappaz B., Breton B., Shaffer E., Turcatti G. Digital holographic microscopy: a quantitative label-free microscopy technique for phenotypic screening. *Combinatorial Chemistry & High Throughput Screening*. 2014;17(1):80–88. DOI: 10.2174/13862073113166660062
- [14] Nadeau L.J., Cho Y.B., Kühn J., Liewer K. Improved tracking and resolution of bacteria in holographic microscopy using dye and fluorescent protein labeling. *Frontiers in Chemistry*. 2016;4(17):1–10. DOI: 10.3389/fchem.2016.00017
- [15] Yi F., Moon I., Javidi B. Cell morphology-based classification of red blood cells using holographic

imaging informatics. Biomedical Optics Express. 2016;7(6):2385-2399. DOI: 10.1364/BOE.7.002385

[16] Kumar, R., Verma, S., & Kaushik, R. (2019). Geospatial AI for Environmental Health:

Understanding the impact of the environment on public health in Jammu and Kashmir. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 1262–1265.